

FACTORS AFFECTING LEARNING MATHEMATICS AMONG GRADE 11 STUDENTS OF NOTRE DAME OF JOLO COLLEGE SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10992523>

ABSTRACT

This study assessed the extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School. It employed descriptive-correlational research design with 100 student-respondents taken through stratified random sampling method. The following are findings of this study: Of the 100 student-respondents, most are aged 16-17, female, and enrolled in the STEM, GAS, or HE CG strands. The majority of the students' parents have a college degree, and an average monthly income between 5,001 and 20,000; The student-respondents often show interest and positive study habits in learning Mathematics, always agree that their math teacher has positive personality traits and teaching skills that influences their learning of Mathematics, often agree that their math teacher uses various instructional materials that enhances their learning of Mathematics, and often agree that home-related factors affect their learning of Mathematics; No significant difference in the extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School when data are grouped according to gender, age, and parents' average monthly income, except for strand, and parents' highest educational attainment; And generally, there is a significant positive correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School, except between home-related factors and interest, personality traits, and teaching skills. This study recommends the following: School heads should provide adequate support and resources for the Mathematics teachers and students, such as hiring qualified and competent teachers, providing sufficient and updated instructional materials, and creating a conducive and stimulating learning environment; Mathematics teachers should enhance their personality traits and teaching skills that foster positive study habits and interest among the students towards learning Mathematics; Mathematics teachers should also

use appropriate and varied instructional materials and methods that suit the needs and preferences of the students and that stimulate their interest and curiosity in Mathematics; Parents should encourage and support their children in learning Mathematics by providing them with a comfortable and quiet study space at home, helping them with their assignments and projects, and motivating them to do their best; Students should develop and maintain positive study habits and interest in learning Mathematics by setting realistic and attainable goals, managing their time and resources effectively, reviewing and practicing their lessons regularly, and seeking help when needed; And future researchers should also investigate the effects of learning Mathematics on the students' academic achievement, career choices, and personal development.

Keywords: *Learning Mathematics, study habits, teaching skills, instructional materials*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics was a fundamental subject that has been a cornerstone of education for centuries. In the human experience, mathematics holds paramount significance. It may be difficult to express anything in the world if mathematical expertise was lacking. Modern Mathematics was widely recognized yet worthless locally. Since the ancient times, Mathematics has been acknowledged as a crucial component of formal education. History demonstrates that early academics created Mathematics by practically solving daily problems. Mathematical development in antiquity was facilitated by outstanding shepherds. The totality of knowledge in science and technology was known as Mathematics (Bed Raj Archarya, et al., 2017). Mathematics was a study of magnitude and number that was highly applicable to almost every discipline. This was because all academic subjects used it to forecast results and solve issues. To conduct domestic and commercial transactions, conduct scientific research, develop technology, solve issues, and make decisions in a range of life situations, a person or a country must be knowledgeable in mathematics.

The belief that "Math is for Males" has played a role in the low number of women in the scientific, engineering, and mathematics fields. There was a common misperception that adult males were the only ones who could benefit from mathematics worldwide (Cvencek et al., 2015). Moreover, boys and girls identify differently in terms of their talents and interests from a very young age due to social perceptions regarding gender and arithmetic prowess (Cvencek et al., 2011). Additionally, by affecting their interests and self-perceptions of their capacity to carry out tasks related to the subject, this may also mediate their learning in the area (Beilock et al., 2010). As stated by Pajares & Schunk (2001) and Farrington et al. (2012), students' self-perceptions of their academic talents are significant because they can affect the amount of effort they put out to accomplish tasks, which helps them adjust to school responsibilities and obligations. Students are more likely to excel in a subject than not if they believe they are excellent in

it, according to Correll (2001). Students who lack the motivation to complete assignments will perform poorly academically (Pintrich, 2000; Ryan). As a result, their academic performance benefits from this. According to Khalaila (2015), more academic achievement was thus closely correlated with a good academic self-concept. As a result, the majority of research suggests that men have a more favorable perception of themselves in mathematics than do women (Kamoru & Ramon, 2017). Additionally, studies show that girls do better than boys on standardized math exams, which are particular evaluations meant to determine students' comprehension and mastery of the subject (Ganley et al., 2013; Spencer et al., 1999). Even though a vast amount of research shows that guys perform better in arithmetic than girls, further research is needed to confirm or refute these findings.

Mathematics has been difficult for the Mabini-NHS school administration and Math teachers to evaluate the poor performance of the kids in the subject. The average mean percentile score (MPS) for the previous three academic years was 54.97, falling short of the 75% passing requirement set by the Department of Education. The MPS dropped to 43.54% in the most recent semester, which raised questions about the students' future. Three primary elements were found when a researcher examined the variables influencing students' success in mathematics: factors related to the students (such as student attitude), factors related to the home (such as family history, education, occupation, and socioeconomic level), and factors related to the teachers (such as teacher effectiveness). Since students' attitudes can shape personal traits that affect their academic success, understanding students' attitudes was essential to understanding students' achievement in Mathematics. Higher achievement and more effort can result from having a positive attitude about the subject. The child's family history, which includes their education, occupation, social-economic standing, and socialization facilities, was one element that was associated to the home. Teachers are the intermediaries between information, values, and skills; hence they are vital in directing students' learning.

Improving the students' capacity to study mathematics required addressing these issues. To establish an atmosphere that inspires students to enjoy mathematics and gives them the tools and resources they need to succeed, educators, parents, and legislators must collaborate. Students who accomplish this will have a solid foundation in mathematics, be able to overcome their fear and anxiety, and grow to love the subject for the rest of their lives.

Learners of mathematics in senior high schools in Jolo are not exempt from the elements that influence the previously described factors. As a result, this study is being done among senior high school students at Notre Dame of Jolo College who are learning the language of mathematics. It gathered actual data to support or refute the extent of aspects related to language learning in mathematics.

Research Questions

This study was set to examine the factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students of Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School.

Specifically, the following problems was systematically answered:

1. What is the demographic profile of Grade 11 students in Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age;
 - 1.2. Gender;
 - 1.3. Strand;
 - 1.4. Parents' highest educational attainment,
 - 1.5. and parents' average monthly income?
2. What is the extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School in the context of:
 - 2.1. Learner-related factors:
 - 2.1.1. Interest, and
 - 2.1.2. Study Habits
 - 2.2. Teachers-related factors:
 - 2.2.1. Personality Traits;
 - 2.2.2. Teaching Skills, and
 - 2.2.3. Instructional Materials
 - 2.3. Home-related factor?
3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School when data are grouped according to their demographic profile?
4. Is there a significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A quantitative research strategy and a descriptive-correlational research design were employed in this study. Research design is the blueprint or road map that directs an investigator in achieving their aims and objectives for the study, according to Babbie and Mouton (2001: p. 75). The study aims to characterize, measure, and draw conclusions about the phenomenon of mathematics learning, the variables that influence math learners, and the significant relationships and variations in these variables when data are sorted according to age, gender, parents' average monthly income, and level of education. Bless and Higson-Smith (1995: p. 63) defined a research plan as "a program that guides a researcher in collecting, analyzing, and interpreting observed facts."

Research Locale

This study was conducted at Notre Dame of Jolo College- Senior high school during the School Year 2023-2024. This secondary school was located in Jolo which was the capital town of Sulu Province.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were the grade 11 students of Dame of Jolo College Senior High School. A total respondent of (at least 100).

Sampling Design

Stratified random sampling was used to get the percentage per strata on grade 11 students. That is, due to access and availability, representative samples Notre Dame of Jolo College-Senior High School were randomly chosen. Subsequently, the fish bowl technique was employed to choose respondents based on grade level by simple random sampling, ensuring that the appropriate amount of data for this study was collected.

Table 1. Total Population of Respondents

STRAND	Population	Sampling Proportion	Sample
ABM	30	15%	5
GAS	202	15%	30
STEM	215	15%	32
HE CG	180	15%	27
BTF	20	15%	3
ICT	20	15%	3
TOTAL	465	90%	100

Data Gathering Procedure

In the collection of data, this study applied the following steps:

- 1) NDJC Senior High School coordinators and principals' offices provided permission to administer the questionnaire.
- 2) A consent from the respondents before administering the questionnaire and,
- 3) The researcher carried out the launch, administration, and retrieval of the questionnaire in person.

Research Instrument

The purposes of the study and the types of data call for necessitate the used of survey as the major data gathering instruments. This research study used a standardized questionnaire developed by **Jennilyn F. Balbalosa** and was used on her research paper entitled “**Factors Affecting Mathematics Performance of Laboratory High School Students at laguna State Polytechnic University**”. The questionnaire was used because of its appropriateness for gathering quantitative information on perceptions. The instrument used a Likert Scale. This type of scale measures attitude by asking study participants to respond to a series of statements about a certain topic. Frequency and percentage was used for the first section of the survey questionnaire asking for the profile of the students. The second part dealt with the collection of data on the extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School.

Statistical Treatment

Statistical tools that were both descriptive and inferential were used to process the data collected for this study, namely:

- 1.) For Research Question Number 1: The profile of the responders was ascertained by using frequency counts and percentages.
- 2) For Research Question No. 2, the mean and standard deviation were used to ascertain the extent to which certain factors affecting the mathematics learning of Grade 11 students at Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School.
- 3) Regarding Research Question Number 3, when data are grouped by gender, the t-test for independent samples is used to find the significant difference in the extent of factors affecting learning mathematics among Grade 11 students at Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) is used to determine the remaining profiles.
- 4) Regarding Research Question Number 4, the significant correlation between the sub-categories subsumed by the extent of factors influencing mathematics learning among Grade 11 students at Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School was ascertained using Pearson's r .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. What is the demographic profile of Grade 11 students in Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School in terms of 1.1 age, 1.2 gender, 1.3 strand, 1.4 parents' highest educational attainment, and 1.5 parents' average monthly income?

1.1 In terms of Age

Table 1.1 presents the demographic profile of the student-respondents in terms of age. The table indicates that out of 100 student-respondents, it highly concentrated in the 16-17 years old group which makes up 92% (92), while 15 years old and below, and 18 years old and above account for 3% (3) and 5% (5), respectively. This implies that most of the student-respondents are in the typical age range for senior high school and that there are fewer students who are younger or older than the average.

Table 1.1 Student-respondents' demographic profile in terms of age.

Age	Number of Respondents	Percent
15 years old and below	3	3%
16-17 years old	92	92%
18 years old and above	5	5%
Total	100	100%

1.2 In terms of Gender

Table 1.2 presents the demographic profile of the student-respondents in terms of gender. The table indicates that out of 100 student-respondents, it skewed toward females who make up 62% (62), while males account for 38% (38). This implies a higher participation or representation of female student-respondents in the surveyed group.

Table 1.2 Student-respondents' demographic profile in terms of gender.

Gender	Number of Respondents	Percent
Male	38	38%
Female	62	62%
Total	100	100%

1.3 In terms of Strand

Table 1.3 presents the demographic profile of the student-respondents in terms of strand. The table indicates that out of 100 student-respondents, STEM has the highest number of respondents who make up 32% (32), followed by GAS account for 30% (30), and HE CG account for 27% (27). ABM, ICT, and BTF have significantly fewer respondents accounting for 5% (5), 3% (3), and 3% (3), respectively. **This implies that the surveyed group is more inclined toward the STEM strand, as well as the GAS strand and the HE-CG strand.**

Table 2.3 Student-respondents' demographic profile in terms of strand.

Strand	Number of Respondents	Percent
STEM	32	32%
GAS	30	30%
HE CG	27	27%
ABM	5	5%
ICT	3	3%
BTF	3	3%
Total	100	100%

1.4 In terms of Parents' Highest Educational Attainment

Table 1.4 presents the demographic profile of the student-respondents in terms of their parents' highest educational attainment. The figure shows that, of the 100 student respondents, 62% (62) had college degrees, and 17% (17) have master's degrees. These parents make up a sizable majority of the respondents. This suggests that the majority of kids come from households with greater access to learning materials, which may have an impact on how well they perform academically.

Table 1.4 Student-respondents' demographic profile in terms of parents' highest educational attainment.

Parents' Highest Educational Attainment	Number of Respondents	Percent	1.5 In
No formal education	4	4%	
Elementary graduate	3	3%	
High school graduate	9	9%	
College graduate	62	62%	
Master's degree	17	17%	
Doctorate degree	3	3%	
Vocational degree	2	2%	
Total	100	100%	

terms of Parents' Average Monthly Income

Table 1.5 presents the demographic profile of the student-respondents in terms of their parents' average monthly income. The table indicates that out of 100 student-respondents, a light majority of 23% (23) have parents whose average monthly income ranges from 10,001 to 15,000, followed by 22% (22) each for those who have parents earning from 5,001 to 10,000 and from 15,001 to 20,000. Only 14% (14) have parents earning 5,000 or less, and 19% (19) have parents earning more than 20,001. This implies that most of the students who comprise 67% come from households with an average monthly income between 5,001 and 20,000 which belong to the low to middle income class.

Table 1.5 Student-respondents' demographic profile in terms of parents' average monthly income.

Parents' Average Monthly Income	Number of Respondents	Percent
5,000 and below	14	14%
5,001 to 10,000	22	22%
10,001 to 15,000	23	23%
15,001 to 20,000	22	22%

20,001 and above	19	19%
Total	100	100%

2. What is the extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School in the context of 2.1 Learner-related factors: 2.1.1 Interest, and 2.1.2 Study Habits, 2.2 Teacher-related factors: 2.2.1 Personality Traits, 2.2.2 Teaching Skills, and 2.2.3 Instructional Materials, and 2.3 Home-related factor?

2.1 In terms of Learner-related factors:

2.1.1 Interest

Table 2.1.1 shows the extent of learner-related factors, specifically interest, affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School. The result shows that the total mean score is 4.06, which indicates an overall rating of “Often”. This means that on average, the student-respondents often show interest in learning Mathematics. The total standard deviation is 0.5129, which indicates that there is some variation among the student-respondents in their interest level.

The mean scores indicate that student-respondents often make themselves prepared for the math subject, always listen attentively and want to get good grades, but sometimes get frustrated or actively participate in discussions. The highest mean score is 4.73, which corresponds to the statement “I want to get good grades on test, quizzes, assignments, and projects.” This implies that the student-respondents have a high **achievement motivation** in learning Mathematics. The lowest mean score is 3.37, which corresponds to the statement “I get frustrated when the discussion is interrupted, or the teacher is absent.” This implies that the student-respondents are not comfortable with situations that are unclear when learning Mathematics.

Table 2.1.1 Extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in the context of Learner-related factor: interest

Statements	Mean	SD	Rating
1. I make myself prepared for the math subject.	4.08	.907	Often
2. I listen attentively to the lecture of my math teacher.	4.64	.578	Always
3. I actively participate in the discussion, answering exercises and/or clarifying things I did not understand.	3.48	1.020	Sometimes

4. I want to get good grades on test, quizzes, assignments, and projects.	4.73	.617	Always
5. I get frustrated when the discussion is interrupted, or the teacher is absent.	3.37	1.143	Sometimes
Total	4.06	.5129	Often

Legend: 4.50-5.00 = Always (A), 3.50-4.49 = Often (O), 2.50-3.49 = Sometimes (S), 1.50-2.49 = Rarely (R), 1.00-1.49 = Never (N)

2.1.2 Study Habits

Table 2.1.2 shows the extent of learner-related factors, specifically study habits, affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School. The result shows that the total mean score is 4.02, which indicates an overall rating of “Often”. This means that on average, the student-respondents often practice positive study habits in learning Mathematics. The total standard deviation is 0.6021, which indicates that there is some variation among the student-respondents in their study habits.

Table 2.1.2 Extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in the context of Learner-related factor: Study habits

Statements	Mean	SD	Rating
1. I do my assignments regularly.	4.40	.853	Often
2. I exert more effort when I do difficult assignments.	4.26	.917	Often
3. I spend my vacant time in doing assignments or studying my lessons.	3.39	1.109	Sometimes
4. I study the lessons I missed if I was absent from the class.	3.92	1.098	Often
5. I study and prepared for quizzes and tests.	4.34	.807	Often
6. I study harder to improve my performance when I get low grades.	4.48	.797	Often
7. I spend less time with my friends during school days to concentrate more on my studies.	3.56	.957	Often

8. I prefer finishing my studying and my assignments first before watching any television program.	3.75	1.058	Often
9. I see to it that extracurricular activities do not hamper my studies.	3.89	.920	Often
10. I have a specific place to study at home which I keep clean and orderly.	4.20	.995	Often
Total	4.02	.6021	Often

2.2 In terms of Teacher-related factors:

2.2.1 Personality Traits

Table 2.2.1 shows the extent of teacher-related factors, specifically personality traits, affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School. The result shows that the total mean score is 4.62, which indicates an overall rating of “Always”. This means that on average, the student-respondents always agree that their math teacher has positive personality traits that affect their learning of Mathematics. The total standard deviation is 0.4672, which indicates that there is less variation among the student-respondents in their agreement with the statements.

Table 2.2.1 Extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in the context of Teacher-related factor: Personality Traits

Statements	Mean	SD	Rating
1. My math teach has a good relationship with the students and teachers.	4.74	.630	Always
2. My math teach shows smartness, confidence, and firmness in making decisions.	4.78	.524	Always
3. My math teach imposes proper discipline and is not lenient in the following the prescribed rules.	4.34	.987	Often
4. My math teach has an appealing personality with good sense of humor.	4.54	.717	Always
5. My math teach is open to suggestions and opinions and is worthy of praise.	4.69	.581	Always

Total	4.62	.4672	Always
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2.2.2 Teaching Skills

Table 2.2.2 shows the extent of teacher-related factors, specifically teaching skills, affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School. The result shows that the total mean score is 4.53, which indicates an overall rating of “Always”. This means that on average, the student-respondents always agree that their math teacher has positive teaching skills that affect their learning of Mathematics. The total standard deviation is 0.5079, which indicates that there is less variation among the student-respondents in their agreement with the statements.

Table 2.2.2 Extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in the context of Teacher-related factor: Teaching Skills

Statements	Mean	SD	Rating
1. My math teach explains the objectives to the lesson clearly at the start of each period.	4.60	0.682	Always
2. My math teach has mastery of the subject matter.	4.74	0.613	Always
3. My math teach is organized in presenting subject matters by systematically following course outline.	4.59	0.668	Always
4. My math teach is updated with present trends, relevant to the subject matter.	4.46	0.797	Often
5. My math teach uses various strategies, teaching aids/devices and techniques in presenting the lessons.	4.27	1.004	Often
Total	4.53	.5079	Always

2.2.3 Instructional Materials

Table 2.2.3 shows the extent of teacher-related factors, specifically instructional materials, affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School. The result shows that the total mean score is 4.004, which indicates an overall rating of “Often”. This means that on average, the student-respondents often agree that their math teacher uses various instructional materials that affect their learning of Mathematics. The total standard deviation is 0.7214, which indicates that there is some variation among the student-respondents in their agreement with the statements.

The mean scores indicate that their math teacher often uses workbooks/textbooks, and articles related to mathematics, uses materials for project development, always uses chalk and blackboard in explaining the lessons, but sometimes uses PowerPoint presentations (visual aids). The highest mean score is 4.71, which corresponds to the statement “My math teach uses chalk and blackboard in explaining the lessons.” This implies that the student-respondents have a high preference for their math teacher’s use of chalk and blackboard as they rate him/her always on this aspect. The lowest mean score is 3.41, which corresponds to the statement “My math teach uses PowerPoint presentations (visual aids).” This implies that the student-respondents have a moderate preference for their math teacher’s use of PowerPoint presentations as you rate him/her sometimes on this aspect.

Table 2.2.3 Extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in the context of Teacher-related factor: Instructional Materials

Statements	Mean	SD	Rating
1. My math teach uses chalk and blackboard in explaining the lessons.	4.71	0.64	Always
2. My math teach uses workbooks/textbooks.	4.15	1.029	Often
3. My math teach uses PowerPoint presentations (visual aids).	3.41	1.571	Sometimes
4. My math teach uses articles related to mathematics.	3.94	1.246	Often
5. My math teach uses materials for project development.	3.81	1.187	Often
Total	4.004	.7214	Often

2.3 In terms of Home-related factors:

Table 2.3 shows the extent of home-related factors, affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School. The result shows that the total mean score is 3.71, which indicates an overall rating of “Often”. This means that on average, the student-respondents often agree that home-related factors affect their learning of Mathematics. The total standard deviation is 0.6251, which indicates that there is some variation among the student-respondents in their agreement with the statements.

The mean scores indicate that student-respondents often use learning materials suitable for their learning, ask for guidance from elders and/or family, do many household chores, get to disturb when using gadgets while studying, have family experience in

financial problem, always motivated by their parents to improve their studies, but sometimes ask for help in their homework, easily get distracted by their friends, get disturb by their siblings, and rarely have tutorial sessions after class. The highest mean score is 4.66, which corresponds to the statement “I am motivated by my parents to improve my studies.” This implies that the student-respondents have a high level of parental support as they rate them always on motivating them to improve their studies. The lowest mean score is 2.38, which corresponds to the statement “I have tutorial sessions after class.” This implies that the student-respondents have a low level of tutorial support as they rate them rarely on having tutorial sessions after class.

Table 2.3 Extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in the context of Home-related factor

Statements	Mean	SD	Rating
1. I am motivated by my parents to improve my studies.	4.66	.655	Always
2. I use learning materials (book, dictionary, and laptop) suitable for my learning.	4.30	.980	Often
3. I have tutorial sessions after class.	2.38	1.462	Rarely
4. I ask for help in my homework.	3.41	1.422	Sometimes
5. I ask for guidance from elders and/or family.	3.50	1.453	Often
6. I easily get distracted by my friends.	3.47	1.259	Sometimes
7. I do many household chores.	4.08	1.089	Often
8. I get disturb by my siblings.	3.38	1.347	Sometimes
9. I get to disturb when using mobile phone/television/radio/gadgets while studying my lessons.	4.23	1.033	Often
10. I have family experience in financial problem.	3.66	1.224	Often
Total	3.71	.6251	Often

3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School when data are grouped according to 3.1 age, 3.2 gender, 3.3 strand, 3.4 parents' highest educational attainment, and 3.5 parents' average monthly income?

3.1 According to Age

Table 3.1 shows, broken down by age category, how several factors affect the degree to which Grade 11 students at Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School learn mathematics. The elements include those that are specific to the student (such as interest and study habits), the teacher (such as personality traits, teaching skills, and instructional materials), and the home environment. The table demonstrates that, at alpha 0.05, none of the factors' F-values or probability values are significant. This means that the perceptions of student-respondents aged 15 and below on the extent of these factors do not differ from those of student-respondents aged 16–17 and 18 and above, or vice versa. This implies that the student-respondents perceive the extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics in the same way regardless of their age. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, “There is no significant difference in the extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School when data are grouped according to age.” is accepted.

Table 3.1 Difference in the extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students when data are grouped according to age.

Sources of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Interest	Between Groups	.610	2	.305	1.164	.317	Not Significant
	Within Groups	25.430	97	.262			
	Total	26.040	99				
Study Habits	Between Groups	.764	2	.382	1.055	.352	Not Significant
	Within Groups	35.130	97	.362			
	Total	35.894	99				
Personality Traits	Between Groups	.522	2	.261	1.200	.306	Not Significant
	Within Groups	21.086	97	.217			
	Total	21.608	99				

	Within Groups						
	Total						
	Between Groups	.535	2	.268			
Teaching Skills	Within Groups	25.002	97	.258	1.038	.358	Not Significant
	Within Groups	25.538	99				
	Total						
	Between Groups	.545	2	.273			
Instructional Materials	Within Groups	50.973	97	.525	.519	.597	Not Significant
	Within Groups	51.518	99				
	Total						
	Between Groups	.529	2	.265			
Home-related Factors	Within Groups	38.156	97	.393	.673	.513	Not Significant
	Within Groups	38.685	99				
	Total						

*Significant at alpha 0.05

3.2 According to Gender

Table 3.2 presents the difference in the extent of various factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School, grouped according to gender. The factors include learner-related factors (Interest and Study Habits), teacher-related factors (Personality Traits, Teaching Skills, and Instructional Materials), and home-related factors. The table shows that the mean difference and probability values for all factors are not significant at alpha 0.05. This means that the extent of these factors does not affect the perceptions of male and female student-respondents differently. This implies that the student-respondents perceive the extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics in the same way regardless of their gender. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, "There is no significant difference in the extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School when data are grouped according to gender." is accepted.

Table 3.2 Difference in the extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students when data are grouped according to gender.

Variables	Grouping	Mean	SD	Mean Difference	t	Sig.	Description
Interest	Male	4.053	0.555	-.0119	-.112	.911	Not Significant
	Female	4.065	0.490				
Study Habits	Male	3.974	0.704	-.0731	-.587	.558	Not Significant
	Female	4.047	0.534				
Personality Traits	Male	4.521	0.587	-.1564	-1.47	.146	Not Significant
	Female	4.677	0.368				
Teaching Skills	Male	4.474	0.512	-.0941	-.898	.371	Not Significant
	Female	4.568	0.506				
Instructional Materials	Male	4.095	0.775	.1463	.985	.327	Not Significant
	Female	3.948	0.687				
Home-related Factors	Male	3.776	0.661	.1118	.867	.388	Not Significant
	Female	3.665	0.603				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

3.3 According to Strand

Table 3.3 presents the difference in the extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School when data are grouped according to strand. The factors include learner-related factors (Interest and Study Habits), teacher-related factors (Personality Traits, Teaching Skills, and Instructional Materials), and home-related factors. The table shows that the F-values and probability values for all factors, except for teaching skills among teacher-related factors, and home-related factors, are significant at alpha 0.05. This means that the perceptions of STEM student-respondents on the extent of these factors differ from those of GAS, and HE CG, or vice versa, as shown in table 3.3.1. However, there is no significant difference in the perception of teaching skills, and home-related factors among the strands. This implies that the student-respondents perceive the extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics differently depending on their strand, except for teaching skills, and home-related factors. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, "There is no

significant difference in the extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School when data are grouped according to strand.” is rejected.

Table 3.3 Difference in the extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students when data are grouped according to strand.

Sources of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Interest	Between Groups	3.281	5	.656	2.71*	.025	Significant
	Within Groups	22.759	94	.242			
	Total	26.040	99				
Study Habits	Between Groups	4.663	5	.933	.281*	.021	Significant
	Within Groups	31.231	94	.332			
	Total	35.894	99				
Personality Traits	Between Groups	2.9	5	.580	.291*	.017	Significant
	Within Groups	18.708	94	.199			
	Total	21.608	99				
Teaching Skills	Between Groups	2.161	5	.432	1.74	.134	Not Significant
	Within Groups	23.377	94	.249			
	Total	25.538	99				
Instructional Materials	Between Groups	8.425	5	1.685	3.68*	.004	Significant
	Within Groups	43.093	94	.458			
	Total	51.518	99				

Home-related Factors	Between Groups	2.409	5	.482	1.25	.293	Not Significant
	Within Groups	36.276	94	.386			
	Total	38.685	99				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

A Post Hoc Analysis using Tukey test is used when data are grouped based on the demographic profile of the students in terms of strand. This is done to find out which groups, categorized based on age, have varying means in terms of interest and study habits under learner-related factors, personality traits and instructional materials under teacher-related factors.

On interest under Learner-related factors: It demonstrates that, when compared to HE CG student respondents, STEM student respondents received a mean difference of .37639* with a Standard Error of .12858 and a p-value of .048 that is significant at alpha 0.05.

On study habits under Learner-related factors: It demonstrates that, when compared to HE CG student respondents, STEM student respondents received a mean difference of .31331* with a Standard Error of .15063 and a p-value of .007, which is significant at alpha 0.05.

On personality traits under Teacher-related factors: The data indicates that among GAS student responders, STEM students obtained a mean difference of .37083* with a Standard Error of .11337 and a p-value of .018 that is significant at alpha 0.05.

On instructional materials under Teacher-related factors: The data indicates that STEM students who responded had a mean difference of .70000* over HE CG students, with a Standard Error of .17693 and a p-value of .002, which is significant at alpha 0.05.

Table 3.3.1 Multiple comparison of Factors Affecting Mathematics Learning by Strand

Dependent Variable	(I) Grouping by Age	(J) Grouping Age	Mean Difference (I - J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Interest	STEM	GAS	.34750	.12505	.070
		HE CG	.37639*	.12858	.048
		ABM	.32750	.23662	.736

		ICT	-.17917	.29711	.991
		BTF	.35417	.29711	.840
		GAS	.33813	.14648	.201
		HE CG	.31331*	.15063	.007
Study Habits	STEM	ABM	.68813	.27719	.140
		ICT	-.43854	.34804	.806
		BTF	.06146	.34804	1.000
		GAS	.37083*	.11337	.018
		HE CG	.05602	.11658	.997
Personality Traits	STEM	ABM	-.02250	.21453	1.000
		ICT	-.19583	.26937	.978
		BTF	.00417	.26937	1.000
		GAS	.27333	.17207	.608
		HE CG	.70000*	.17693	.002
Instructional Materials	STEM	ABM	.58000	.32560	.483
		ICT	-.03333	.40883	1.000
		BTF	-.10000	.40883	1.000

*The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level

3.4 According to Parents' Highest Educational Attainment

Table 3.4 presents the difference in the extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School when data are grouped according to parents' highest educational attainment. The factors include learner-related factors (Interest and Study Habits), teacher-related factors (Personality Traits, Teaching Skills, and Instructional Materials), and home-related factors. The table shows that the F-values and probability values for all factors, except for study habits under learner-related factors, instructional materials under teacher-related factors, and home-related factors, are significant at alpha 0.05. This means that the perceptions of student-respondents whose parents are college graduates on the extent of these factors differ from those whose parents are elementary graduates, hold master's degrees, and have no formal education, or vice versa, as shown in table 3.4.1. However, there is no significant difference in the perception of study habits, instructional materials, and home-related factors among the groups. This implies that the student-respondents

perceive the extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics differently depending on their parent's highest educational attainment, except for study habits, instructional materials, and home-related factors. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, "There is no significant difference in the extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School when data are grouped according to parents' highest educational attainment." is accepted.

Table 3.4 Difference in the extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students when data are grouped according to parents' educational attainment.

Sources of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Interest	Between Groups	3.686	6	.614	2.556	.025*	Significant
	Within Groups	22.354	93	.240			
	Total	26.040	99				
Study Habits	Between Groups	3.574	6	.596	1.714	.126	Not Significant
	Within Groups	32.320	93	.348			
	Total	35.894	99				
Personality Traits	Between Groups	3.324	6	.554	2.818	.015*	Significant
	Within Groups	18.284	93	.197			
	Total	21.608	99				
Teaching Skills	Between Groups	5.832	6	.972	4.588	.000*	Significant
	Within Groups	19.705	93	.212			
	Total	25.538	99				
Instructional Materials	Between Groups	4.814	6	.802	1.598	.157	Not Significant
	Within Groups	46.704	93	.502			
	Total	51.518	99				
Home-related Factors	Between Groups	1.779	6	.296	.747	.613	Not Significant
	Within Groups	36.906	93	.397			

*Significant at alpha 0.05

The study employed a Post Hoc Analysis using Tukey test to determine which groups classified according to parents' highest educational attainment have different levels of mean in the areas of personality traits, teaching skills, and the degree of interest under learner-related factors, personality traits under teacher-related factors, and so on. The data were grouped based on the demographic profile of the respondents and students.

On interest under Learner-related factors: According to the data, there was a mean difference of .92059*, a Standard Error of .27245, and a p-value of .018 between student respondents who did not possess a master's degree and those who did. At alpha 0.05, this difference is significant.

On personality traits under Teacher-related factors: The information shows that, in comparison to respondents whose parents have completed elementary school, student respondents without formal education have a mean difference of -1.08333* with a Standard Error of .33865 and a p-value of .030; in contrast, respondents whose parents have completed high school have a mean difference of -.97222* with a Standard Error of .24640 and a p-value of .008; in comparison, respondents whose parents have completed college have a mean difference of -.76290* with a Standard Error of .22874 and a p-value of .020; and respondents who possess a master's degree have a mean difference of -.82059* with a Standard Error of .24640 and a p-value of .021 in comparison to those who have finished college. At alpha 0.05, each of these deviations is significant.

On teaching skills under Teacher-related factors: According to the data, there is a significant difference at alpha 0.05 between student respondents whose parents have no formal education and those whose parents have a college degree (mean difference = -.76129*, standard error = .23746, p-value = .029, and mean difference = -.89412*, standard error = .25580, p-value = .012).

Table 3.4.1 multiple comparison of Factors Affecting Mathematics Learning by parents' highest educational attainment.

Dependent Variable	(I) Grouping by Age	(J) Grouping Age	Mean Difference (I - J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Interest	No formal education	Elementary graduate	-1.11667	.37445	.054
		High school graduate	-.58333	.29462	.434

		College graduate	-.68226	.25292	.110	
		Master's degree	-.92059*	.27245	.018	
		Doctorate degree	-.98333	.37445	.130	
		Vocational degree	-.75000	.42459	.574	
Personality Traits	No formal education	Elementary graduate	-1.08333*	.33865	.030	
		High school graduate	-.97222*	.26645	.008	
		College graduate	-.76290*	.22874	.020	
		Master's degree	-.82059*	.24640	.021	
		Doctorate degree	-.88333	.33865	.135	
		Vocational degree	-.45000	.38399	.903	
		No formal education	Elementary graduate	-.93333	.35157	.122
			High school graduate	-.77778	.27661	.084
Teaching Skills		College graduate	-.76129*	.23746	.029	
		Master's degree	-.89412*	.25580	.012	
		Doctorate degree	-.66667	.35157	.488	
		Vocational degree	.50000	.39864	.871	

*The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level

3.5 According to Parents' Average Monthly Income

Table 3.5 shows the variation in the degree of factors influencing mathematics learning among Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School students in Grade 11 when the data are sorted by average monthly income of the parents. The elements include those that are specific to the student (such as interest and study habits), the teacher (such as personality traits, teaching skills, and instructional materials), and the home environment. The table demonstrates that, at alpha 0.05, none of the factors' F-values or probability values are significant. This means that the perceptions of student-respondents whose parents' average monthly income is between 10,001 to 15,000 on the extent of these factors do not differ from those whose parents' average monthly income is below 5,000, between 5,001 to 10,000, 15,001 to 20,000, and above 20,000, or vice

versa. This implies that the student-respondents perceive the extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics in the same way regardless of their parents' average monthly income. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, "There is no significant difference in the extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School when data are grouped according to parents' average monthly income." is accepted.

Table 3.5 Difference in the extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students when data are grouped according to parents' average monthly income.

Sources of Variation		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Interest	Between Groups	1.713	4	.428	1.672	.163	Not Significant
	Within Groups	24.327	95	.256			
	Total	26.040	99				
Study Habits	Between Groups	.432	4	.108	.289	.884	Not Significant
	Within Groups	35.462	95	.373			
	Total	35.894	99				
Personality Traits	Between Groups	.317	4	.079	.353	.841	Not Significant
	Within Groups	21.291	95	.224			
	Total	21.608	99				
Teaching Skills	Between Groups	.192	4	.048	.180	.948	Not Significant
	Within Groups	25.345	95	.267			
	Total	25.538	99				
Instructional Materials	Between Groups	1.974	4	.493	.946	.441	Not Significant
	Within Groups	49.544	95	.522			
	Total	51.518	99				

Home-related Factors	Between Groups	1.546	4	.387	.989	.418	Not Significant
	Within Groups	37.139	95	.391			
	Total	38.685	99				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

4. Is there a significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School?

Table 4 shows the relationship between the subcategories included under the scope of factors influencing the mathematics learning of grade 11 students at Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School. The table indicates that all of the calculated Pearson correlation coefficients (Pearson r) between these variables are significant at alpha 0.05, with the exception of the correlations between interest, personality traits, and teaching skills and home-related factors. Particularly, Grade 11 pupils at Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School exhibit connections to varying degrees among the sub-categories that fall under the umbrella of factors influencing mathematics learning. These include:

- 1) Moderate positive correlations between Interest and Study Habits, Personality Traits, a low positive correlation between interest and Teaching Skills, and Instructional Materials.
- 2) Moderate positive correlations between study habits and teaching skills, instructional materials, and home-related factors, a low positive correlation between study habits and personality traits.
- 3) High positive correlations between personality traits and teachings skills, a low positive correlation between personality traits and instructional materials.
- 4) Moderate positive correlations between teaching skills and instructional materials.
- 5) Moderate positive correlations between instructional materials home-related factors.

This means that as one variable increases, the other variable also tends to increase, and that these relationships are not likely to be random. The strongest correlation is between Personality Traits and Teaching Skills ($r = 0.640$, $p < 0.01$), which implies that students who have favorable personality traits for learning Mathematics also tend to perceive their teachers' skills as high. The weakest correlation is between Interest and Home-related Factors ($r = 0.185$, $p = 0.065$), which suggests that students' interest in Mathematics is not strongly influenced by their home environment. The other correlations are not significant which means that there is no linear relationship between the variables. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, "There is no significant

correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students in Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School.” is rejected.

Table 4 Correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of factors affecting learning Mathematics among Grade 11 students.

Variables		Pearson	Sig.	N	Description
Dependent	Independent	r			
Interest	Study Habits	.463*	.000	100	Moderate
	Personality Traits	.353*	.000	100	Moderate
	Teaching Skills	.207*	.039	100	Low
	Instructional Materials	.266*	.008	100	Low
	Home-related Factors	.185	.065	100	Low
Study Habits	Personality Traits	.264*	.008	100	Low
	Teaching Skills	.323*	.001	100	Moderate
	Instructional Materials	.400*	.000	100	Moderate
	Home-related Factors	.409*	.000	100	Moderate
Personality Traits	Teaching Skills	.640*	.000	100	High
	Instructional Materials	.205*	.041	100	Low
	Home-related Factors	.150	.135	100	Low
Teaching Skills	Instructional Materials	.314*	.001	100	Moderate
	Home-related Factors	.079	.438	100	Very High
Instructional Materials	Home-related Factors	.420*	.000	100	Moderate

*Correlation coefficient is significant at alpha .05

Correlation Coefficient Scales Adopted from Hopkins, Will (2002):

0.0-0.1 = Nearly Zero; 0.1-0.3 = Low; 0.3-0.5 = Moderate; 0.5-0.7 = High; 0.7-0.9 = Very High; 0.9-1 = Nearly Perfect

Conclusions

The study concludes that:

- 1) The majority of student-respondents are ordinary seniors in high school, from low-to middle-class backgrounds, with bachelor's degree-holding parents.
- 2) Student-respondents have a positive study habits and interest towards learning Mathematics, which is influenced by their math teacher's personality, teaching skills, and instructional materials, as well as their home environment.
- 3) The student-respondents' gender, age, and parents' average monthly income have no significant influence on how they perceive the extent of factors affecting their learning of Mathematics among Grade 11 students in Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School, except for their strand and parents' highest educational attainment.
- 4) Student-respondents' interest, study habits, personality traits, teaching skills, and instructional materials are interrelated and influence each other in the process of learning Mathematics. The only exception is the home-related factors, which do not show a significant relationship with any of the other sub-categories.

Recommendations

This study recommends the following:

- 1) School heads should provide adequate support and resources for the mathematics teachers and students, such as hiring qualified and competent teachers, providing sufficient and updated instructional materials, and creating a conducive and stimulating learning environment.
- 2) Mathematics teachers should enhance their personality traits and teaching skills that foster positive study habits and interest among the students towards learning Mathematics.
- 3) Mathematics teachers should also use appropriate and varied instructional materials and methods that suit the needs and preferences of the students and that stimulate their interest and curiosity in Mathematics.
- 4) Parents should encourage and support their children in learning Mathematics by providing them with a comfortable and quiet study space at home, helping them with their assignments and projects, and motivating them to do their best.
- 5) Students should develop and maintain positive study habits and interest in learning Mathematics by setting realistic and attainable goals, managing their time and resources effectively, reviewing and practicing their lessons regularly, and seeking help when needed.
- 6) Future researchers should also investigate the effects of learning Mathematics on the students' academic achievement, career choices, and personal development.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

First and foremost, each participant received a thorough informed consent form outlining the study's objectives, procedures, possible benefits and hazards, and confidentiality guidelines. Moreover, in instances where the trial outcomes were unaffected by the respondents' personal details, every trial data point was meticulously anonymized. To protect participant privacy, data collection was done in a private setting, and the gathered information was stored in a safe archive that the researchers alone could access. Each member was respected in the same spirit even though their opinions and views differed. The researchers also tried to provide a friendly and safe space for the participants so they could discuss candidly about their experiences.

Acknowledgments

The researcher would like to extend his deepest gratitude to all the people who helped him in any manner, who have shared the effort and knowledge in order to make this research a reality.

To Jesus Christ, our Lord and Savior, for giving the wisdom, strength, and knowledge in exploring things, for the guidance in helping surpass all the trials that he encountered and for giving determination to pursue his study, and make this study possible.

He would like to express his deep and sincere gratitude to his research adviser **MR. RICKY S. MORALES, JR., MA-MATH**, for the continuous support to his study and research, for his patience, motivation, enthusiasm, and immense knowledge.

To the Board of panels, to **PROF. CHARISMA S. UTUTALUM, Ed.D., CESE**, SSC President for her words of encouragement, **ASSOC. PROF. MASNONA S. ASIRI, DPA**, Dean of Graduate Studies, and to **PROF. NELSON U. JULHAMID**, Vice President for Academic Affairs, for their efforts, understanding, and constructive comments and suggestions for the enrichment of the study.

To **MRS. FATIMA SHAINA S. DAMMANG, LPT, MAE**, Principal of Notre Dame of Jolo College Senior High School, for her approval in allowing him to conduct the study in her reputed institution and likewise to the senior high school students who exerted efforts and time in answering the questionnaires which were very crucial for the completion of this study.

Finally, he extremely grateful to his parents, for their love, prayers and sacrifices for educating and preparing him for his future. He is very much thankful to Ms. Satrana I. Malik, and Ms. Mary Queen Z. Loria for their continuous support to complete this research work.

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